

D3.3 Cognitive empathic HMI Design and Implementation

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Author	Kahina AMOKRANE-FERKA (IRTSX), Clara Mussault (IRTSX),		
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About AWARE2ALL

Facing to the challenge of future highly automated vehicles, where occupants can freely orient themselves to engage in non-driving activities. This new environment prompts questions about how car occupants will actually sit, what activities they will engage in, and how they will be informed through the HMI to keep them in the loop if necessary.

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) deployment in traffic, by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and changes in the interaction of different road users caused by the emergence of HAV through the development of innovative technologies along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies.

AWARE2ALL will develop safety and HMI systems that will be interrelated through achieving a holistic understanding of the scene to ensure safe operation of the HAV. AWARE2ALL proposes a common conceptual universal safety framework for considering Human Machine Interaction (HMI). The project will be built on the results of projects funded under H2020 and other R&D programmes addressing the identification of new safety-critical situations and the most likely positions and postures considering the expected HAV applications.

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

AWARE2ALL includes 16 partners from 6 EU Member States (ES, DE, GR, NL, FR and SE) and 2 associated countries (TR, CS) and it is complemented by the International Advisory Board (IAB) representing key stakeholders that covers the full research and industrial development automotive value chain, more specifically in the CCAM field.

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Executive Summary

The AWARE2ALL project represents an initiative aimed at enhancing road safety and operational efficiency in the context of Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs). By leveraging cutting-edge technology and innovative methodologies, the project seeks to address critical challenges associated with the deployment of HAVs, focusing on key areas such as safety assessment frameworks, Human-Machine Interface (HMI) systems, and real-world demonstrations across various European sites.

As the name of the AWARE2ALL project suggests, one of the main objectives is to address the needs of all types of drivers, with or without disabilities. Thus, the design approach aims to be human-centric and inclusive, ensuring that the use of HAV benefits everyone, or at least the personae involved in Demo 3, such as young persons and older persons with hearing impairments. Furthermore, the design of Adaptive HMIs, that adjust to the driver's cognitive state, measured in real-time by Occupant Monitoring System, enhances this human-centric approach. This seeks to tailor the interaction to the driver's current condition, potentially providing a safer and more individualized driving experience.

This deliverable presents the demonstrator with the designed and implemented iHMI systems. We will present the different devices with their technologies as well as synchronization and adaptability policies and rules.

First, we will present the different HMI assets one by one, then we will present a complete scenario with the evolution of the iHMIs according to the context (persona, driver state, external environment).

Acronyms and terms

Dissemination level	
AD	Autonomous driving
CWL	Cognitive Workload
DMS	Driver Monitoring System
DR	Driver Readiness
HandsOn/Off	Hands On or Off Steering Wheel
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
iHMI	Internal Human-Machine Interface
MD	Manual Driving
MM	Manual Mode
MRM	Minimum Risk Manoeuvre
NDRT	Non-Driving Related Task
NDRA	Non-Driving Related Activity
OMS	Occupant Monitoring System
Pre-TOR	Pre-alert before Take Over Request
SA	Situation Awareness
TOR	Take Over Request
ToC	Transition of Control
LED	Light Emitting Diode
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
STW	Steering Wheel

1.Introduction

Purpose of the deliverable

This document is the written form of deliverable D3.3, which is of type DEMO, under the nomenclature of Europe deliverable types: D3.3 is a set of iHMI prototypes developed in WP3. This document summarizes the main features of these iHMIs

The deliverable presents multimodal and adaptive Human Machine Interfaces (HMIs), highlighting their role in improving interaction between the driver and the automated vehicle. These HMIs combine several communication channels (visual, auditory, haptic) to offer an intuitive, accessible and secure experience. They adapt to users' needs and cognitive states, based on various parameters such as readiness, cognitive workload and situational awareness.

Adaptability is made possible by Occupant Monitoring Systems (OMS), which analyse indicators such as gaze direction, physiological signals and hands position on the steering wheel. The aim is to optimize situational awareness and reduce cognitive load, by preparing the driver, particularly in non-emergency recovery scenarios (freeway exit).

These HMIs are inclusive, designed to meet the needs of all drivers, including the elderly and deaf, based on the principles of universal design. They promote user confidence in automation, reduce cognitive load and ensure a smooth transition between autonomous and manual driving.

The content of this deliverable is dedicated to iHMI. The sections 2 to 6 describe HMI and the logic of the communication with the driver in Automated car (Demo 3) and section 7 describes the HMIs and their logic of the communication with passengers in the autonomous shuttles (Demo2)

This deliverable is highly related to:

- **D3.1 Occupant state and behaviour analysis and iHMI.** There, the technologies implemented are explained. More scientific and detailed description is included in D3.1.
- **D3.2 In-Cabin integration of OMS technologies and components.** There the description of the developed OMS (Occupant Monitoring System) prototypes and their implementation into the different testing facilities are presented.
- **D2.1 AWARE2ALL Systems requirements.** This is a description of refined use cases and based on that, the requirements for the system as well as the detailed test scenarios for demonstrators.
- **D5.1. Assessment framework.** this document presents a holistic view of the project's milestones, insights gathered, and the path forward.

Intended audience

The dissemination level of D3.3 is public. Primarily, this document intends to showcase the prototypes developed during the AWARE2ALL project regarding iHMIs.

D3.3 Cognitive empathic HMI Design and Implementation

Our demonstrator presents the innovative internal Human-Machine Interface (iHMI) designed to enhance the driving experience by seamlessly integrating advanced technologies and intuitive user interaction. These HMIs are intended to be adaptive in order to address specific driver needs and states, such as Driver Readiness, Cognitive Workload, Situation Awareness.

This document is primarily intended for individuals with a background in technology and the automotive industry, particularly HMI designers and human factors specialists. However, it is open to anyone interested in the project and its results.

2. User Needs

2.1 Introduction

The emergence of automated vehicles on the road introduces new challenges, particularly in terms of communication between the vehicle and its driver. In mixed traffic situations, where roles may alternate between manual and automated driving, it is essential that the driver, whether active or in supervisory status, has a clear understanding of the vehicle's status, intentions and limitations. This bidirectional communication is fundamental to maintain vigilance, prevent misunderstandings and ensure swift (smooth) transition of control in case of necessity. By developing intuitive and inclusive human-machine interfaces (HMIs), we can facilitate this interaction and reinforce driver trust in these new technologies, while improving safety on the roads.

In automated driving (L3/4), drivers must be ready to regain control at any time, for example at a freeway exit or junction, when the system triggers a takeover request (TOR). During this process, acquiring an optimal driver state is crucial, mainly: acquiring a certain level of situational awareness, which includes perception and understanding of road and traffic conditions, a necessary condition for making immediate decisions. It is also possible to guide occupants to an optimal state as the environment evolves, by providing a new cognitive and empathic human-machine interface.

The Society of Automotive Engineers has defined 6 levels of automation (Figure 1) [SAE, 2021]. The level 0, L0, corresponds to fully manual driving. At level 1 (L1), the system takes over longitudinal or lateral control of the vehicle. In Level 2 (L2), vehicles are considered partially automated, as the system controls both the longitudinal and lateral movements of the vehicle. L0, L1 and L2 correspond to Manual Driving (MD). Between L0 and L2, the driver remains the main actor in driving, whereas from level 3 onwards, since they can engage in Non-Driving Related Tasks (e.g., reading, watching a video, playing a game) without supervision, they can be considered as passenger or occupant, at least until they have to take back control in L3 and L4.

FIGURE 1: SAE J3016 LEVELS OF DRIVING AUTOMATION

In this project, the car in our cockpit is equipped with L0 (MD) and L3/4 (AD) levels.

Driving Level	Description
L0 (MD)	No automation
L3/4 (AD)	High-level automation. Eyes-Off, Hands-Off. Automated system does not know how to take a freeway exit/junction, the Minimum Risk Maneuver (MRM) is performed under the responsibility of the system, if the driver fails to regain control.

TABLE 1: THE DEMO 3 CAR DRIVING LEVELS

2.2 User Needs in Manual (L0) and Automated (L3/4) Driving

2.2.1 MD Mode

In Manual Driving mode (MD), the driver is active and thus, he is an actor of the driving task. He is seated facing the steering wheel, hands on the wheel, and presumably looking at the driving scene. However, he must remain alert regarding the dynamic moving environment. If multiple senses (vision, hearing, haptics) are involved in the driving activity, the visual modality is central. Therefore, the driver's gaze will shift to several external areas, as well as to the vehicle's various devices (like cluster, Head-Up Display (HUD), central screen, lighting, mirrors...), to gather information. The driver must also be attentive to different sounds from the outside environment (horns, noises, ...) and inside the car (assistance alert, music, passenger conversations, etc.). This will have to be considered in the design and implementation of iHMI so as not to overload the driver with signals, and to maintain efficiency.

2.2.2 AD Mode

Automated Driving mode (AD), particularly L3/4 level of SAE, introduces a new paradigm for driving activity: previously assisted in driving, the driver can now detach his attention and all various human functions involved in driving from any other task, delegating all driving activity to the system (under certain conditions). Therefore, the driver can be considered passive regarding driving (being just a vehicle occupant) when the system is in control. However, although the human driver could do other things than driving, there are at least two considerations to bear in mind when designing internal HMI in AD:

- The driver must be informed which automated mode is activated, and have access to other information that he/she deems useful or might reassure him/her,
- The driver must be able to resume the driving task or take over at any time (in our case, especially when the system requires it).

2.2.3 Take-Over Request situation

In AD mode, particularly at SAE Level 3, when the system detects the necessity, it requests the driver to take back control of the vehicle, providing him with a more or less extended lead time depending on the urgency of the situation. The system triggers this request in response to changes in driving or system conditions that require driver intervention. These conditions may include approaching a highway exit, navigating complex road infrastructure such as junctions, etc. The TOR

is intended to ensure a smooth transition from automated to manual control, allowing the driver sufficient time to assess the situation and take appropriate action. This transition of control impacts directly situational awareness, which is defined as the ability to perceive, understand and anticipate future states of the environment and the automated system [Endsley, 1995].

In recent works, this TOR phase is divided into two warning stages with different objectives. The first warning (i.e. the information stage) is designed to inform drivers to be alerted to potential hazards on the road, rather than requiring them to perform manoeuvres immediately. The second warning (i.e. the warning stage) requires drivers to act, such as braking, accelerating or turning the steering wheel [Bai, 2024; Ma, 2020].

The attentional load involved in processing the TOR is distributed between the driver's different resources [Wickens, 2008]. To this end, several modalities can be used to alert drivers, including visual, auditory and haptic signals. In our study, multimodality is primarily implemented to address inclusion needs, ensuring that alerts and interactions are accessible to a diverse range of drivers with different needs and restrictions. To provide effective communication and interaction, human-machine interfaces (HMIs) must be both adaptive and synchronized with the driving context. They must adjust in real time to the driver's needs and cognitive state, while providing clear, relevant information at the right time. Such adaptability and synchronization are essential for smooth decision-making.

2.2.4 Minimum Risk Manoeuvre situation

Minimum Risk Manoeuvre is an automated safety procedure designed to minimize traffic risks when a driver fails to respond to a transition demand or in case of vehicle failure. During this manoeuvre, the system gradually slows down the vehicle within its lane or follows a safe trajectory if lane markings are not visible, considering surrounding traffic and infrastructure. The deceleration is controlled to not exceed 4.0 m/s^2 to ensure a smooth and safe stop [R157 ALKS]. In this MRM situation, the driver needs to be informed about the manoeuvre and its consequences. This includes not only the triggering of the MRM, but also its implications, such as the gradual slowing down of the vehicle, its stopping in a safe place, and the need for the driver to regain control.

To conclude on driver needs and according to ISO 15008:2017, driving activity, in a manual mode, is already a complex task involving interactions between various functions and skills: physical functions (e.g. holding the steering wheel, pressing on the pedals); cognitive functions (e.g. attention, perception, vigilance, information processing and decision making, memory); somatosensory (e.g. body sensations) and sensory functions (e.g. sensory modalities like vision, hearing, haptics, and their integration); visual functions (e.g. distance and trajectory estimation using visual-spatial skills) and psychomotor functions (e.g. sensori-motor or cognitive-motor coordination, emotions and tonico-emotional reactions). Other physiological (e.g. reaction time, fatigue, stress, mental workload) or behavioral factors (e.g. driving habits, level of experience, respect of safety rules) are important to consider on the driver's perspective during a driving task, whether in manual or automated mode. This approach of human functioning is just one piece of the puzzle, and it will be necessary to coordinate this with other parts of the automotive driving system, such as the car and the dynamic environment.

3.HMI Enablers

To ensure multimodal interaction and communication, the vehicle is equipped with several internal HMI enablers as shown in Figure 2, following the description of each one.

FIGURE 2: HMI ENABLERS

3.1 Cluster

The cluster is the essential visual interface, located in the driver's focal field of vision when driving. Usually in a classic car, it represents an essential interface between the vehicle and the driver. It brings together all the information needed for driving (such as speed and engine rpm, fuel and range monitoring, alerts and diagnostics, etc.). For automated driving, emphasis lies on communicating system status, current and planned manoeuvres, and environmental object detection. This aligns with the broader perspective outlined in [Beggiato, 2015], advocating for the presentation of system status, reliability, navigation, speed, limits, and critical scenarios across all automation levels [Richardson, 2017]. In [Diels, 2016], the authors investigated other types of information that passengers expected from highly automated or fully autonomous driving: vehicle intentions related to hazardous scenarios, upcoming vehicle manoeuvres, speed limits in speed restricted areas, whether it is safe to proceed, hazard detection and the ability to override or confirm.

According to this short state of the art, a wireframe mock-up consisting of four main zones is developed (Figure 3):

- At the top, the speed zone displays the vehicle's speed in real time as well as the speed limit.

- Just below, the Immediate Driving Environment zone is located, which is dedicated to information related to the driving environment, the road lanes, the ego vehicle, the surrounding cars, in some context, textual messages, countdown, etc.
- On the left side, the navigation zone provides contextual information related to the navigation, next manoeuvre type, distance to change direction, etc.
- On the right side, the Human-system Task allocation zone presents the current driving mode (icon), the availability of AD mode, the car state (driving, park, etc.).

FIGURE 3: MAIN ZONES OF THE CLUSTER

3.2 . LEDS – Lighting

LEDS can be used to offer customers a pleasant experience, as is already the case in modern cars, which are increasingly equipped with ambient lighting (e.g. BMW, Audi). LEDS can also be used to attract the driver's attention, in his peripheral vision, to convey information from the system to the human (for example, to draw his attention to a specific area or alert the driver to an upcoming manoeuvre).

Even in MD, the system can help the driver in providing information such as warning of an overtaking in progress. The LEDs can be green, indicating an informatory level message, and also similar to the color of the turn signals, indicating the desire to change lanes or overtake; in order to keep a certain consistency between signals [CMI, 2020].

In our case, lighting is used to indicate current driving mode. Therefore, several possibilities are considered, for example changing colour and animation: 1. green lighting colour for indicating the manual mode 2. turquoise lighting colour for indicating the automated mode, 3. orange colour to indicate the TOR phase, 4. red colour to indicate MRM phase.

In our cockpit, the LEDs are placed on the windshield, along the entire width of the vehicle, and at the bottom of the windows on each side, left and right (as is often the case for ambient lighting kit).

3.3 Speakers

Research in cognitive psychology indicates that sound effectively complements visual information by attracting peripheral attention and plays a crucial role in emotional experience, intuitive interaction and situational awareness. And in environments such as the car cockpit, an auditory message can be a more effective vector of warning or information than its visual equivalent. In the context of automated driving, auditory warnings are widely used. These warnings are generally classified into two categories according to their characteristics: vocal-based (e.g. speech and spearcons) and non-vocal-based (e.g. earcons and auditory icons). Some studies conclude that certain auditory warnings can enhance driver response times and effectiveness in critical situations [Misdariis, 2021; Li, 2024]

To this end in our cockpit we opt for two kinds of auditory messages: tones and vocal messages.

- Tones can be with different tonalities, frequencies and rhythms. They can indicate the urgency of a message, distinguishing, for example, the final 10 s of a take-over request from the first request at 20 s or initial pre-warning at 60 s.
- Vocal messages are generated by an AI audio platform called ElevenLabs, which converts text into spoken speech.

The different auditory messages are broadcast on the car's speakers

3.4 Haptic Actuators

Haptic stimulation will be utilized as a mode of multimodal communication for the driver and occupants, such as for take-over requests. This stimulation will be delivered through haptic devices, providing vibrotactile feedback, for instance. The feedback will be integrated into the seat, targeting the back, or into the steering wheel. As auditory tones, these haptic signals can indicate the urgency of a message, distinguishing, for example, the final 10 s of a take-over request from the first request at 20 s or initial pre-warning at 60 s.

3.4.1 Haptic Seat

A Haptic Seat Cover offers several advantages: it eliminates the need for accessories (like haptic wearables), is flexible in terms of installation (unlike embedded actuators) and provides the most reliable contact surface in an autonomous driving scenario. Additionally, this large contact surface allows for a rich variety of patterns (e.g. movement, spatial differentiation left/right). The removable seat cover is equipped with vibration motors from Precision Microdrives. This system is implemented by CEA, then integrated in Demo3.

Initial testing was conducted to select suitable vibration motors from a wide range of options. The primary requirement was an actuator that delivers stimulation that is neither uncomfortable nor painful, and can be perceived through the seat cover. We selected a motor with eccentric rotating masses (24 mm diameter) operating at a high frequency (at 3 V, the amplitude is 3.4 G and frequency 240 Hz). Tests were conducted to determine the optimal positioning of the vibration motors, ensuring a balance between sensitivity and comfort. The Haptic Cover-Seat is equipped with 12 independent vibrotactile motors.

FIGURE 4: HAPTIC COVER SEAT (12 VIBROTACTILE MOTORS)

The system's hardware is controlled by a microcontroller (Raspberry Pi) and can receive commands from any device connected to the same network (e.g. the HMI Manager). The haptic seat system includes a predefined library of vibrotactile patterns. A wide variety of patterns have been registered and tested to deliver a range of messages (e.g., warnings, alerts, notifications).

We designed and tested a set of patterns for driving monitoring scenarios. In the following picture, each dot corresponds to a vibration on one of the actuators of the seat. It is possible to change the position, the intensity of the vibration and the duration. It is possible to change the vibration to change the message criticality level behind it: more or less urgency, indicate a right-left, front-back or up-down location.

- Driver monitoring: drowsiness and situation of no-awareness :

The goal of the feedback is to get back the driver's attention on the road and if needed "wake" him/her up gradually, depending on the level of drowsiness.

- First level : The idea here is to have more of a "tickle" effect that stimulates without being too unpleasant and attracts attention without being too urgent.

- Second level: Idea of sending very strong stimulations to wake the person up and indicate a strong urgency. Repetitions to force a feeling, based on a "warning", giving the idea of someone "tapping" or shaking the person, in bursts.

- driver monitoring: Lane Changing scenario: When the driver is changing lanes, the system checks whether there is an incoming vehicle and its distance to ensure the lane change is safe. If it is not, the user gets warned depending on the severity of the danger (i.e. depending on the distance to the vehicle) and depending on his/her persistence to pursue with the course of action. The feedback could be localized on the side of the danger/lane change, and in our case, it can be also used to guide on the new direction to take
- Medium risk: repetition and increasing intensity are used here to increase the level of urgency. A single vibrator is always used for a moderate vibration, such as an alert.

- High risk: The upper part of the seat was assigned to the more critical messages, to encourage people to look towards the danger, the "naive idea" of moving closer to the head to direct the gaze. In comparison with previous models, the level of urgency is increased by the additive side, which increases the perceived intensity.

3.4.2 Haptic steering wheel

The haptic feedback in the steering wheel is generated using a Senso-Wheel SD LC, which employs a low-inertia direct-drive motor to produce torque in the steering wheel. This torque is essential for the Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) system as part of the simulator, providing the driver with realistic kinesthetic and vibrotactile feedback from the virtual environment. Instead of incorporating external vibration devices into the steering wheel, the LC motor itself is used to generate haptic feedback.

This approach allows for seamless integration into the system, eliminating the need for external devices and ensuring a clean, compact setup. This system is implemented by Tecnia

FIGURE 5: SENSO-WHEEL SD LC INSTALLED IN THE SYSTEM X SIMULATOR

At Tecnia, as shown in **Figure 6**, an identical Senso-Wheel was procured to ensure compatibility with the System X simulator. This setup facilitated the development and testing of haptic feedback "icons" directly on the Senso-Wheel, which were later integrated into the simulator.

FIGURE 6: SENSODRIVE STEERING WHEEL USED TO DEVELOP THE HAPTIC ICONS AT TECNALIA

The designed haptic feedback (shown in **Figure 7**) provides the driver with fast and effective alerts through steering wheel vibrations while not disturbing the rest of the passengers. Three types of haptic alerts were developed to address different driving situations:

1. Notification Alert: Used to indicate that the AD system is available.
2. Transition Alert: Confirms that a handover between manual and autonomous driving has occurred (in HMI design, also used for the reverse transition, from autonomous to manual driving, after a successful driver take-over).
3. TOR Alert: Warns the driver that, in five seconds, the AD system will stop functioning, requiring manual driving to resume.

These alerts use distinctive vibration waveforms designed to be easily distinguishable. Their duration, intensity, and pattern were iteratively refined to balance urgency, clarity, and driver comfort. The

timeline of haptic feedback activation is shown below, illustrating how the alerts are synchronized with different driving events.

FIGURE 7: WAVEFORMS OF THE HAPTIC FEEDBACK IN THE STEERING WHEEL

Use of the haptic feedback in the steering wheel

At the start, when the vehicle is in manual mode, a haptic notification signals that AD is available, ensuring the driver is aware of the system’s readiness. Once AD is activated, a transition alert confirms the successful handover, marking the shift from manual to autonomous mode. As the timeline progresses, the system approaches the TOR phase, where the driver is required to resume control. At TOR1 (20 s), there is no haptic TOR, as it is not urgent to resume control and the driver may not have the hands on the steering wheel. After that, the second TOR2 (10 s) is launched, if the driver still has not done the handover, 10 s to the end of Operation Design Domain (ODD), the haptic TOR is launched, with an escalated intensity. This progressive use of haptic alerts ensures that the driver is effectively guided through critical transitions, complementing visual and auditory cues while maintaining focus on the driving task.

FIGURE 8: TIMELINE OF THE USE OF THE HAPTIC FEEDBACK IN THE STEERING WHEEL

Tests in Demo3 simulator

Figures 9, 10, 11 illustrate the torque response of the steering wheel in the Demo3 simulator during a Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) drive in SCANer Studio. The response is evaluated in terms of torque rather than position, as the sensation felt by the driver’s hands is primarily influenced by force rather than movement. The vibrations generated by the steering wheel motor were manually calibrated by a driver through direct inspection of the system. This subjective evaluation ensured the vibrations were pleasant, sufficiently strong to be clearly perceived, and easily distinguishable. At the same time, the driver ensured that the vibrations did not interfere with the driving experience, cause instabilities, or disrupt the steering system. Given that the same motor controlling the vibrations is also responsible for the lateral movement of the vehicle, the calibration process focused on maintaining proper lateral control while ensuring no unintended lateral displacement occurred.

As shown in the figures, the resulting torque does not fully reach the specified torque reference. However, each pulse in the reference signal is faithfully replicated in the output, and the waveform pattern remains clearly distinguishable. This was confirmed through manual testing by the driver,

who evaluated the vibrations by hand. Despite minor deviations from the reference, the driver could clearly perceive the intended haptic feedback pattern, ensuring its effectiveness during operation.

FIGURE 9: RESPONSE OF THE HAPTIC NOTIFICATION

FIGURE 10: RESPONSE OF THE TRANSITION ALERT

FIGURE 11: RESPONSE OF THE TOR2

3.5 Central display

The central display, for this moment, is used as a support to the game (2048 game) that the driver will perform when the car is in automated mode.

4. Use Case transition of control with the different user experience steps

The detailed description of the meta scenario is described in D5.1.

Below is a description of the driving scenario implemented in Demo 3.

Most of the driving will take place on a 6 km three-lane highway (Figure 12). In the initial step, the driver begins driving in manual mode in an insertion lane, then must merge onto the highway as soon as possible. To reach AD availability, he must change lanes to the middle one and then activate AD mode. Once the activation of AD mode has been confirmed, the driver can perform an NDRT (Non-Driving Related Task) for few minutes (4 to 5 minutes) until there is a system request to take over. In this scenario the TOR is due to an upcoming change of direction and the reaching of ODD limits. If the driver regains control in time, he must change lanes to the left in order to successfully take the new direction. If the driver does not take over within the allotted time, the system will perform an MRM (Minimum Risk Manoeuvre).

FIGURE 12: PRINCIPAL STEPS OF THE SCENARIO

Like symbols or traffic signs (e.g. traffic lights signal) whose meanings transcend borders and languages, colours also carry significant messages. Thus, as the scenario timeline illustrates, we've used colours according to their common meaning:

- The green colour thus conveys the sense of movement, action or authorization, and we could associate it with manual mode, where the human driver controls the vehicle and is the actor in the driving activity (while the automated system is passive). Some automakers have already made the choice of green colour for representing MD mode (like Honda Legend 2021).
- The turquoise colour, as recommended by the SAE, will be used to indicate that AD mode is on, as other automakers (Mercedes Bentz, BMW, Honda, ...) already did.
- Orange refers to being attentive to a situation, an obstacle or a change. This colour choice has already been used by some automakers with the "hands on the wheel" icon displayed on screens at the time of Take-Over Request, or with LEDs (sometimes flashing for greater saliency) on the steering wheel or inside the car (Honda Legend, Mercedes-Bentz EQS, BMW

D3.3 Cognitive empathic HMI Design and Implementation

7 Series 2024, etc.). The colour orange intensifies as the urgency to regain control grows. The double orange colour signifies that the TOR is associated with the issue of graduating signals based on their urgency.

- Red refers to danger, urgency and stopping. It will be for the MRM.

Consequently, visual signals (on cluster or LEDS) will change colour according to the steps of the scenario.

5. Baseline HMI

In this section, we will describe the HMIs and our choices for the reference interface without adaptability, common to all situations and driver states.

5.1 HMI Logic

The results of the Design Thinking session (D1.2) were considered. The needs of the two personae, Rose and Uma, were taken into account.

FIGURE 13: THE TWO PERSONAE OF THE DEMO3

To this end, the design is done by considering personae Rose (old person, with hearing impairments such as hearing loss or deafness) and Uma (young person). To do so, we considered in our design the different principles of inclusive design as described in Institute for Human Centered Design [IHCD].

Inclusive design is a design methodology that aims to create products, services, and environments accessible and usable by the widest possible range of people, regardless of their abilities, age, cultural background, or other factors. This approach moves beyond traditional accessibility considerations, striving to accommodate diverse user needs from the outset of the design process [Persson, 2015]. Inclusive design not only provides support for people with specific needs, but also enhances the overall user experience (e.g., subtitles improving accessibility for people in noisy environments, ramps benefiting parents with strollers or travelers with luggage, non-slip tactile strips on metro platforms enhancing safety for both visually impaired individuals and all passengers, etc.). It points out that inclusive design reduces the gap between users and products, resulting in improved satisfaction and usability for diverse populations [Patrick, 2021]. Multimodal iHMI, while essential for ensuring inclusive design, has also demonstrated its benefits.

The combination of different sensory modalities improves the way automated vehicles inform and warn the driver during critical situations such as takeover requests (TOR) and shortly after the switch from Automated Driving (AD) to Manual Driving (MD) [CMI, 2020].

The system can use various communication modalities to transmit information to the driver specifically in TOR. Visual displays provide clear information that helps the driver understand the messages, and auditory warning in addition to vocal messages complement visual displays. Lights and haptic feedbacks are also used to attract the driver's attention.

5.2 HMI Requirements & Design

This section gives an overview of the different needs, requirements and designs according to each driving phase.

5.2.1 Initial Manual Mode

In MD mode the driver is the responsible of the driving task, so the cluster is bringing together all the information needed for driving (speed, speed limit, some navigation information, etc.). The Table 2 summarise some needs, requirements and illustration that we propose.

Needs	Requirements	Illustration
Clear information on parking status	P Symbol highlighting (P for parking) Gray color on the cluster Textual welcome message	Figure 14
Clear information on manual mode	D Symbol highlighting (D for drive) MD icon (steering wheel with hands on) on the cluster Green color for the lighting and margins of the cluster	Figure 15 Figure 17
Clear information about AD availability, conditions,	Flashing icon in cluster and flashing borders of the cluster Tone + vocal message "Automated Mode Available" Haptic steering wheel AD notification"	Figure 17 Figure 16
Intuitive activation procedure	Explanation how to activate AD in Vocal and textual message on cluster: "push on steering wheel bouton to activate AD mode" Previous explanation + possibly one LED on the button to facilitate learnability or usability	

TABLE 2: NEEDS, REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGNS IN MD MODE

FIGURE 14: CLUSTER IN INITIAL PHASE (PARKING)

FIGURE 15: CLUSTER IN MD MODE WITH AD NOT AVAILABLE

FIGURE 16: CLUSTER IN MD MODE WITH AD AVAILABLE

FIGURE 17: LEDS IN MD MODE

5.2.2 Automated Mode

In AD mode, the driver is engaged in non-driving-related tasks, leading to reduced vigilance and situation awareness with difficulty in shifting attention when he has to regain control of the car.

Therefore, in AD mode, the cluster, in its central part, reproduces the perspective of the road and surrounding vehicles, to inform the driver in real time of the current driving situation (since he is out of the driving loop). This view of the cluster could also help to restore driver’s situational awareness during the TOR preparation phase.

Needs	Requirements	
Have a confirmation from system about AD activation	Vocal message “Automated Mode Activated” Haptic steering wheel “AD transition” With a little delay (~5 to 7s), an additional vocal message such as a suggestion to “Release the steering wheel and start the game”	Figure 18
Good perception of mode change (MD to AD)	Turquoise color (cluster + LEDs) Icon related to AD mode (instead of MD mode)	Figure 19
Access to information on the current driving environment (surroundings vehicles, navigation, tec.), while the system is in charge of driving.	Ego vehicle in its environment, its lane, with vehicles around	Figure 18

TABLE 3: NEEDS, REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGNS IN AD MODE

FIGURE 18: CLUSTER IN AD MODE

FIGURE 19: LEDS IN AD MODE

In our design, the takeover request (TOR) is characterized by two stages. Firstly, pre-TOR, an extended prewarning stage to enhance driver's readiness, notifying him of the forthcoming need to regain control of the vehicle, when he was previously disengaged from driving and distracted by other tasks (Non-Driving Related Task). Secondly, TOR itself, requesting the driver to take control of the vehicle to return to a manual mode in which he must actively drive.

Since the TOR situation lasts 60 s, it is possible to propose several levels or graduations of alerts. Below, details and illustrations are provided with the Pre-TOR at 60 s, TOR 1 at 20 s and TOR 2 at 10 s.

5.2.3 Pre-TOR as a preparation of TOR

During the pre-TOR stage, drivers are provided with information about an upcoming takeover event but are not immediately required to take over.

Needs	Requirements	Illustration
Be informed of upcoming direction change and be aware of the necessity to take over soon.	Textual message on cluster "End automated section in 2km – get ready" Flashing turquoise LED Tone + vocal" End automated section in 2km – get ready" Haptic Seat vibration	Figure 20

TABLE 4: NEEDS, REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGNS IN PRE-TOR PHASE

FIGURE 20: CLUSTER IN PRE-TOR PHASE

5.2.4 TOR period

When TOR 1 is triggered, the system sends a request to the driver to immediately take control of the vehicle. At TOR 2, since the urgency is greater, signals must be gradually increased in intensity and become more salient (e.g. reinforced orange, stronger haptic feedback, countdown in the cluster).

Needs	Requirements	Illustration
<p>Have clear information about the take over request sent by the system</p>	<p>TOR 1 - At 20 seconds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cluster borders in orange Textual message on the cluster + Icon TOR 1 (hands on steering wheel in orange) Orange LED Non-vocal message with urgent tone + Vocal message Haptic feedback in seat <p>TOR 2 - At 10 seconds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cluster borders in more highlighted orange Textual message on the cluster + Icon TOR 2 (hands on steering wheel in highlighted orange) Countdown on the Cluster Orange-Red LEDs Non-vocal message alert with progressive urgency increase + Vocal message "Drive now" Haptic feedback in steering wheel 	<p>Figure 21 Figure 22</p> <p>Figure 23 Figure 24</p>

	Haptic feedback in seat with urgency increase and rhythm	
Intuitive de-activation procedure	Previous explanation + activated LED on the button to facilitate learnability or usability	
Clear information on current localization and planned destination (as an explanation of the need to take over)	On the left side of the cluster, Next manoeuvre type + remaining distance to the left junction	Figure 21 Figure 23

TABLE 5: NEEDS, REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGNS IN TOR PHASE

FIGURE 21: CLUSTER IN TOR PHASE AT 20 SECONDS

FIGURE 22: LEDS IN TOR PHASE AT 20 SECONDS

FIGURE 23: CLUSTER IN TOR PHASE AT 10 SECONDS

FIGURE 24: LEDS IN TOR PHASE AT 10 SECONDS

5.2.5 Manual Mode after TOR

As soon as the driver takes over and regains control, the driving becomes manual again. It must be ensured that the driver well understands that he is back in charge of driving, in various ways (e.g. green LEDs and cluster, haptic steering wheel feedback, vocal message).

Needs	Requirements	Illustration
Clear information on manual mode activation	D Symbol highlighting (D for drive) Cluster borders in green MD icon (steering wheel with hands on) on the cluster Textual message Green LEDs Vocal message "Manual Mode Activated" Haptic steering wheel "MD transition"	Figure 25

<p>Clear information on the destination to take</p>	<p>On the left side of the cluster, next manoeuvre type + remaining distance to the left junction</p> <p>At the centre of the cluster, visual guide of the manoeuvre to be performed (lane change) (A highlighting on the destination on the immediate driving environment).</p> <p>Vocal message "Take left lane, direction Rouen-Poissy"</p> <p>Haptic Seat left vibration</p>	<p>Figure 26</p>
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FIGURE 25: CLUSTER IN MD ACTIVATED JUST AFTER TOR (BEFORE CHANGING LANE)

FIGURE 26: CLUSTER IN FINAL MD AFTER CHANGING LANE

5.2.6 Minimum Risk Maneuver

At the end of TOR phase, if the driver did not take over, the system launches the Minimum Risk Maneuver, where it brakes and then pulls to one side and stops.

Needs	Requirements	Illustration
<p>Clear information on MRM phase: risky situation, vehicle</p>	<p>Red general color in the cluster</p> <p>Textual message on the cluster</p> <p>Non-vocal message with urgent tone</p>	<p>Figure 27, Figure 28</p>

slowdown to stop in some seconds	Vocal message Haptic feedback in seat	
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TABLE 6: NEEDS, REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGNS IN MRM PHASE

FIGURE 27: CLUSTER IN MRM PHASE

FIGURE 28: LEDS IN MRM PHASE

6. Adaptive HMI

Beyond the multimodal and inclusive design of internal HMIs, one of the objectives of the user tests planned as part of demo 3 is to evaluate the added value of adaptive human-machine interfaces, which adjust in real-time to the driver’s cognitive state, compared to baseline, non-adaptive HMIs.

6.1. Introduction to adaptive HMI

An adaptable system is one that allows the user to change its parameters in order to operate accordingly, whereas an adaptive system will automatically adjust to the user’s assumed needs (Opperman, 1994). In our study we based on the last one.

The researchers in [Feigh, 2012] proposed a two-part framework for the design of an adaptive system. They categorized ways in which adaptive systems can modify their behaviour (Figure 29) and characterized trigger mechanisms through which adaptive systems can sense the current situation and decide how to adapt (Figure 30).

FIGURE 29: TAXONOMY OF ADAPTATIONS FOR HUMAN-MACHINE SYSTEMS [FEIGH, 2012]

FIGURE 30: TAXONOMY OF TRIGGERS FOR ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS [FEIGH, 2012]

Based on these taxonomies, our approach primarily focuses on modifying interaction and Task Scheduling within the taxonomy of adaptation. This enables a dynamic change when tasks are performed, including their duration and priority. And also, adjustments in communication between the car and the driver by addressing key aspects such as how information is conveyed, where control transitions occur, and when interactions take place. Particular synchronisation is placed on the timing of information delivery, effective transition of control, and driver engagement to ensure seamless and intuitive communication between the vehicle and the driver. Regarding the taxonomy of triggers, we consider factors such as operator measurements (in particular with the driver’s readiness

value, provided by the Decision Making Module, which “integrates data from multiple system components to ensure a holistic readiness assessment” D3.2); environment state (exit to take, time before TOR, etc.) system state and mode (AD, MD, TOR, etc.). Additionally, we explore how adaptive interaction can adjust both the timing of interactions and interface features.

6.2. Adaptive HMI in automated driving

Adaptive multimodal interaction allows automated cars to effectively communicate with drivers, ensuring safety, minimizing distractions. Adaptability is a key capability to support the driver’s performance, to enhance driver’s experience and to improve trust in the automated system. It can be achieved by integrating various interaction modalities, among others. However, interfaces and interaction may vary depending on driving context like environmental conditions (road traffic, weather, etc.), driver’s state (cognitive and physical), variety of population (young and old drivers) and other situational factors.

In general, before TOR triggering, both internal and external information about the driver’s state and the driving situation should be gathered to guarantee a safe outcome. This is particularly important in takeover processes that are required in emergency situations. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the driver’s physical and mental state, that can be correlated with information related to current road situation. The complexity involves factors influenced by the driver’s individual cognitive adaptation processes, affecting the response to a Takeover Request (TOR). This includes the driver’s state, such as vigilance, cognitive workload and situational awareness in connection to non-driving Related Tasks (NDRT).

In the literature, researchers have already addressed the issues of sensory modality combinations and their dynamic adaptation to the driver’s state and the driving situation. For example, in [Leung, 2024], the authors concluded that compared to implicit HMI (non-adaptive HMI), the use of explicit HMI (adaptive HMI) did not lead to inappropriate actions associated with the driving role. In the same way, Diederichs et al [Diederichs, 2020] proposed an adaptive HMI framework, able to support driver state monitoring-based transitions in automated driving. They applied it on several use cases to study the impact of adaptive HMI to driver state (anxiety, physical fatigue, etc.) and driving situation (Road works); Even if user testing is not done, the conclusion is that this framework and system architecture provide a promising approach to enhance driver and rider assistance systems.

In the same perspective, our objective in AWARE2ALL project is to shed light on the impact of the adaptivity of the HMI on user experience. The aim is to assess the contribution of HMIs that adapt to the driver’s state (readiness, situational awareness and cognitive load) to improve situational awareness and cognitive load, as well as their impact on the user’s experience and trust when resuming driving.

6.3. HMI Manager: Input and outputs

The HMI manager is a rule-based system. Its aim is to choose the appropriate HMIs and the timing according to the driving situation (AD, speed, highway exit, etc.) and more specifically to the driver state (Driver readiness, Situation Awareness, Cognitive Workload, etc.). For this module, our principal objectives are:

- Improving the driver’s readiness to intervene in transition of control after a takeover request

- Provide appropriate interfaces to interact with the driver.

The HMI Manager takes as input, multiple data on the driver’s cognitive state, measured by various OMS modules (D3.2), and produces as output, HMIs that are adapted to these measured states (Figure 31).

FIGURE 31: INPUT AND OUTPUT OF HMI MANAGER

To achieve this, we have adopted two distinct adaptation of HMIs in order to improve driver readiness, situation awareness and reduce cognitive workload. As the first, we have chosen the timing to build an adaptation strategy based on the Driver Readiness value. In the second one, driver’s situation awareness, cognitive workload and HandsOn/Off status are taken into account to determine each information to communicate.

6.4 HMI Manager logic

The first strategy of the HMI manager focuses on adaptively preparing the driver for the Take Over Request (TOR) phase by considering their cognitive state.

During a TOR situation, when the system requests the driver to regain control, the transition from a Non-Driving Related Task (NDRT) to active driving can be cognitively demanding. To minimize this, a preparation period is introduced through a pre-alert, notifying the driver in advance of the upcoming request in our case, taking over control to change direction to the left. This pre-alert was implemented in both the baseline and adaptive conditions to ensure a comparable level of preparation.

However, a pre-alert alone may not be sufficient for effective preparation, and different driver behaviors may emerge [Bay, 2024; Tan, 2023]. Some drivers may react immediately to the pre-alert, while others might delay their preparation to complete an ongoing NDRT, such as finishing a challenging game,

To address this issue, thanks to OMS modules, pre-alerts, in adaptive HMI, can be repeated or reissued according to driver’s cognitive state. This ensure that preparation for the TOR is as effective as possible. By minimizing delayed responses that can be risky, and promoting a gradual rather than abrupt reconstruction of situational awareness. The goal is to enhance both performance and driver experience during the TOR phase. Conversely, the system also prevents unnecessary alerts to avoid overloading driver who is already preparing to resume control.

For this adaptation of pre-TOR (as a preparation of TOR), the HMI Manager takes as input the driver’s readiness value (%), since it represents a “holistic readiness”, and based on this, applies the corresponding rule to produce the associated output, which is the repetition of pre-TOR at a variable timing.

The driver’s readiness, provided by the Decision-Making Module (see deliverable D3.2), is a percentage between 0 and 100, with three defined thresholds: Low (0-30%), Medium (30-70%) and High (70-100%).

After the launch of the common (baseline and adaptive HMI) pre-alert, HMI Manager observes the measured driver’s readiness and applies the associated rules (Figure 32):

- If the driver’s readiness is low, maybe because the driver does not perceive the pre-alert or postpones the preparation, it appears necessary to send a second pre-alert early enough to not lose the benefits of the preparation phase regarding the reconstruction of situational awareness or mental workload management.
- If the driver’s readiness is medium, a second pre-tor could be sent halfway through the preparation period as a reminder to prepare the upcoming request.
- If the driver’s readiness is high, a second pre-tor could be sent just a few seconds before the TOR request, just in case.

FIGURE 32: ADAPTIVE PREPARATION OF TOR ACCORDING TO DRIVER’S READINESS THRESHOLDS

Then, a second adaptation strategy can occur, not as a preparation but around the TOR, because other data on the driver’s state is available, such as the presence of hands on the steering wheel, eyes on the road, etc. If this is not the case, a reminder could be sent, to be as ready as possible to resume driving when the system sends the TOR request. If, for example, the driver's eyes are still on the game, then the system encourages him to rebuild his situational awareness with a vocal, non-vocal and text message to pay attention to the road and the environment (watch the road, you're about to take over). According to preparation stage, this can be accompanied by seat vibration. If the driver already has his eyes on the road but he doesn't have his hands on the wheel, the system will ask him to put his hands on the wheel with a vocal, textual message and icon on the cluster.

6.5 Adaptive HMI requirements & design

As with the baseline HMI, adaptive HMI must be inclusive. This means that the needs of different driver profiles have already been taken into account (or at least tried to be) in the baseline. So, all additional communications must be multimodal, to be perceived by all personae without exception, but without overloading them either. Thus, to ensure inclusivity, modalities will not be used here as a means of adapting to the cognitive state, even if this may have been attempted in some way [Wickens, 2008].

For the logic design of the HMIs in pre-TOR and TOR phases, we adopted the ACT-R cognitive model in which the takeover process and the phases of situational awareness were defined. This model represents the evolution of the cognitive process when taking back control, where the recognition and early sensory-motor patterns run in parallel. Regaining control begins with visual reorientation and gaze fixation on the control signal, with the aim of interrupting secondary activity (NDRT) by the driver, then moving his/her hands to the steering wheel and feet to the pedals. The driver continues with a visual reorientation with gaze fixed on the centre of the road, followed by a wider reorientation towards the road environment, and finally by fixation on the relevant elements of the road scene, before deactivating automated driving [Scharfe, 2019].

The main means of adaptation is the addition of a second pre-alert during the TOR preparation (or Pre-TOR), and its timing, variable according to driver’s readiness. The timings (T60 – nominal pre-alert [CMI, 2020; Bai, 2024]; T50 – low readiness ; T35 – medium readiness ; T25 – high readiness) still need to be tested to verify the proper synchronization of the alerts and the intervals between them.

So, to choose information and modalities to communicate, HMI manager based on Situation Awareness (SA), Cognitive Workload (CWL) and HandsOn/Off (HO). The information to be provided depends on the state of the driver and the progress made in this phase of preparation for regaining control (PreTOR).

Needs	Requirements	Illustration
<p>The driver needs to have a minimum level of readiness</p> <p>The driver needs to rebuild his situation awareness (have information about the environment,</p>	<p>At T60 seconds</p> <p>Non-vocal message “Informative tone 1”</p> <p>Vocal message “Change of direction in 2 km. Manual driving soon required”</p> <p>At T35 seconds</p> <p>Non-vocal message “Informative tone 2”</p> <p>Vocal message “Change of direction in 1 km! Start preparing to regain control!”</p> <p>At T25 seconds</p> <p>LED animation on the windshield</p>	

<p>next maneuver, etc.)</p> <p>The driver needs to have an appropriate cognitive load</p>	<p>Non-vocal message "Informative tone 3"</p> <p>If the driver did not react:</p> <p>Vocal message "Change of direction in 500 m! Start preparing to regain control!" then "Stay concentrated. Observe the road and road users".</p> <p>Textual message "'Change of direction in 500 m, prepare to retake control"</p> <p>Seat vibration to encourage the driver to get a look on this left</p> <p>If the driver does not have his hands on the steering wheel:</p> <p>Vocal message "put your hands on the steering wheel, Stay concentrated. Observe the road and road users"</p> <p>Animation icon to put hands on the steering wheel</p>	
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TABLE 7: SOME NEEDS, REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGNS FOR ADAPTIVE HMI

7. HMI design for autonomous shuttles

7.1. Introduction to HMI for autonomous shuttles

The HMI for autonomous shuttles serves as a critical communication bridge between the vehicle and its passengers, ensuring safety, comfort, and clear information delivery. The system should provide real-time updates on shuttle operations, including the current status, destination and intermediate stations, but also informative content such as weather forecast and news, through visually engaging panels and informative audio announcements.

By combining dynamic visuals, such as maps and status indicators, with synchronized audio messages in multiple languages, the HMI enhances accessibility for diverse users. A user-centered design ensures clarity in communication, reduces anxiety during autonomous travel, and aligns with the shuttle's goal of delivering a seamless, intuitive, and enjoyable passenger experience.

To achieve this, a questionnaire is proposed to identify the preferences of future shuttle passengers with the goal to reduce anxiety related to driverless autonomous shuttles during normal driving conditions and emergency situations.

7.2. Basic structure

The audio-visual Human-Machine Interface (HMI) for the autonomous shuttle should be designed to ensure passenger safety, comfort, and clear communication throughout the journey. The system shall provide real-time updates on shuttle operations, including the current driving status, upcoming stations, and other information such as weather forecast through visually engaging panels and synchronized audio announcements in multiple languages.

The HMI shall adapt dynamically to various operational states, such as normal driving, approaching or stopping at a station, and degraded modes during reduced visibility or technical issues. It also shall communicate critical safety states like emergency stop-stay or emergency stop-leave, ensuring passengers are informed and guided appropriately in urgent situations.

Additionally, the system shall enhance passenger experience by integrating safety notifications, smooth transitions between operational states, and consistent updates to instil confidence in the shuttle's autonomous operation. By combining safety-focused features with user-centric design elements, the HMI should contribute to a reliable and comfortable journey for all passengers.

There are several approaches for HMIs in autonomous vehicles. Probably the most structured and efficient approach is based on a state machine. Alternative approaches include behaviour trees, which offer more flexibility than state machines by allowing parallel decision-making, and AI-based models, which can create adaptive HMIs that learn from user preferences and environmental conditions. A hybrid approach combining a state machine with AI or rule-based systems can provide both predictability and adaptability especially in highly dynamic and context-aware interfaces. As the intended use is in autonomous shuttles, we were opting for a hybrid approach using a state machine for structured state management and a rule-based system for dynamic decision-making enabling a more intelligent, adaptive, and user-friendly HMI.

A hybrid approach combining a state machine and a rule-based system can significantly enhance the flexibility, adaptability, and safety of a Human-Machine Interface (HMI) for autonomous shuttles

while ensuring compliance with automotive safety standards such as ISO 26262 (functional safety) and ISO 21448 (safety of the intended functionality).

In this approach, the state machine manages the shuttle's primary operating states, such as Waiting for Passengers, Driving, Stopping for Obstacles, and Emergency Stop. It enforces strict transitions between these states, ensuring structured and deterministic behaviour. This prevents unintended actions and guarantees safe operations. Meanwhile, the rule-based system operates within each state, allowing the HMI to dynamically adjust based on real-time conditions such as passenger occupancy and behaviour, weather, and traffic.

One of the main advantages of this hybrid method is its ability to combine predictability with adaptability. The state machine ensures clear and controlled transitions, keeping the shuttle's operations aligned with safety requirements, while the rule-based system enables real-time adjustments within each state. For example, in the Waiting for Passengers state, the HMI can display different messages depending on the number of passengers boarding or whether accessibility features are needed.

This approach also enhances user interaction by providing context-aware feedback. Instead of rigid, predefined messages, the rule-based system refines how the HMI communicates with passengers and operators. Another key benefit of this approach is its scalability and maintainability. New rules can be introduced or updated without modifying the entire state machine structure. This makes it easier to adapt to evolving regulatory requirements, technological advancements, and user feedback.

A real-world example of this approach in autonomous shuttles can be seen in the interaction between passengers and the HMI. The state machine ensures that the shuttle follows a structured workflow, such as stopping at designated locations and handling emergency situations safely. Meanwhile, the rule-based system enhances adaptability by adjusting the user interface based on passenger feedback, road conditions, or special circumstances like priority boarding for mobility-impaired individuals.

In conclusion, using a hybrid approach that combines a state machine for structured state management with a rule-based system for dynamic decision-making allows for a more intelligent, adaptable, and user-friendly HMI in autonomous shuttles. By integrating safety standards such as ISO 26262 and ISO 21448, this approach ensures that the interface remains reliable, secure, and compliant, while improving overall passenger experience, operational efficiency, and adaptability to real-world conditions.

FIGURE 33: MINIMUM CONFIGURATION OF THE STATE MACHINE FOR THE AUTONOMOUS SHUTTLE HMI; THE RULE-BASED PART IS NOT SHOWN FOR VISIBILITY.

7.3. Requirements and design

The design of an HMI for autonomous shuttles must prioritize clarity, accessibility, and real-time feedback to ensure a seamless passenger experience especially in safety-related situations. A user questionnaire, which will be presented in WP5, helps gather insights from diverse passengers, including individuals with disabilities, to create an intuitive and inclusive interface. Key requirements include clear visual and auditory feedback, real-time updates on vehicle status, route, and safety alerts, and optionally multi-modal interaction (touchscreens, voice commands, and physical buttons). A reduced version of such an HMI will be implemented in demonstrator 2 of Aware2All, which is an autonomous driverless shuttle.

Accessibility features such as high-contrast displays, text-to-speech support, and animated icons enhance usability for all passengers. The questionnaire process involves surveying users, analyzing feedback, and prototyping layouts. Based on user input, the HMI is optimized for application in an autonomous shuttle.

By aligning with classical automotive safety standards, the interface should ensure safety compliance while maintaining a user-friendly experience. A continuous improvement approach based on passenger feedback enables iterative refinements, ensuring that the autonomous shuttle HMI remains intuitive, inclusive, and efficient for all users.

FIGURE 34: EXAMPLE LAYOUT FOR NORMAL DRIVING SHOWN IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE.

FIGURE 35: EXAMPLE LAYOUT FOR NORMAL DRIVING DYNAMICALLY ADAPTED FOR REDUCED VISIBILITY SHOWN IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE.

8. Conclusions

In this deliverable, we have presented the HMIs we have designed for two different implementations: one for an automated vehicle and one for an autonomous shuttle. For the automated vehicle we mainly implemented visual and haptic HMIs, as well as some of the state of the art that inspired us. We have also presented the baseline and adaptability logics. A guiding scenario has been described, with the different HMI choices at each stage, as well as the logic of the HMI manager by taking into account the outputs of the OMS modules. To validate the proposed HMIs and the adaptive strategies, user testing are planned involving 30 end-user on demo3. Each participant will experience both the baseline and the adaptive HMIs, within transition of control use case, to facilitate a comprehensive comparison (for more details related to the evaluation protocol see deliverable D5.2)

For the autonomous shuttle (demonstrator 2) no specific user tests are planned as only the technical team of Tecnalía is allowed to ride with this shuttle. Nevertheless, some subjective feedback may be gathered from these tests to further improve the HMI such a vehicle in the future. This is the reason why the questionnaire for an HMI in autonomous shuttle is covering a wider area to be deployed in other configurations of autonomous vehicles.

9. References

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